

Mass Univariate Aggregation Methods for Machine Learning in Neuroscience

Fatemeh Doshvargar^{1,2}, Fabricio Cravo^{2,3}, Hallee Shearer^{2,3}, Stephanie Noble^{1,2,3,4}

1. Department of Bioengineering, Northeastern University
2. Institute for Cognitive & Brain Health, Northeastern University
3. Department of Psychology, Northeastern University
4. Department of Radiology & Biomedical Imaging, Yale

Abstract

Machine learning plays a crucial role in neuroscience and has been advancing our ability to achieve precision medicine goals, particularly in individualizing diagnosis and treatment. However, the high dimensionality of fMRI data poses significant challenges for constructing interpretable predictive models. However, several established methods, such as Connectome-based Predictive Modeling (CPM) or Polygenic Risk Scores (PRS) estimation, which have been recently translated into the neuroimaging context for the Polyneuro Risk Score or Polyconnectome Scoring (PNRS; PCS), offer an interpretable approach, which we term “Mass Univariate Aggregation” (MUA). In sum, they use a linear combination of weighted features and evaluate each feature independently, enabling the identification of a specific predictive connection. Despite the existence and widespread usage of various MUA approaches in neuroimaging, tools for their application are still fragmented, and there does not yet exist an open-access unified tool for implementing and evaluating these models together within a standardized machine learning workflow. Here, we present a unified, flexible, and accessible configurable pipeline that can be used for implementing CPM, PNRS, and many new MUA configurations facilitated by user-specified parameters. Built in Python as an add-on for scikit-learn, our configurable pipeline enables researchers to leverage the functionality and standards provided by a widely used open-access machine learning tool. We demonstrate that the designed configurable pipeline effectively replicates the outcomes achieved by existing CPM and PNRS implementations, utilizing resting-state functional connectivity data from the Human Connectome Project to predict fluid intelligence ($n = 1067$). Additionally, although designed to fill a gap in neuroimaging, our open-source, configurable pipeline provides a standardized platform for applying the MUA methods to any machine learning setting that features high-dimensional data.

Keywords: functional MRI; interpretable machine learning; univariate; connectome-based predictive modeling; polygenic risk score; scikit-learn; open-source software

1. Introduction

Machine learning serves as a crucial tool in neuroscience for enhancing our understanding of the human brain. The application of machine learning to neuroimaging data enables researchers to extract meaningful information from brain data and build predictive models that capture individual differences in brain-behavior relationships ([Marek et al., 2022](#); [Scheinost et al., 2019](#)). However, the high dimensionality of neuroimaging data, where the number of features often vastly outnumbers observations, presents significant analytical challenges ([Varoquaux & Thirion, 2014](#); [Marek et al., 2022](#)). Multiple machine learning methods that involve mass univariate regression followed by aggregation, which we term Mass Univariate Aggregation (MUA), have been introduced and demonstrated to effectively balance predictive performance with interpretability in high-dimensional data ([Pervaiz et al., 2020](#)).

MUA methods represent a class of approaches that perform individual statistical tests on each feature separately (mass univariate), then combine weighted features into a unified predictive model (aggregation) (e.g., [Shen et al., 2017](#); [Byington et al., 2023](#); [Libedinsky et al., 2024](#); [Choi et al., 2020](#)). This philosophy underlies several successful methods across different fields. As an example, Polygenic Risk Scores (PRS), originally developed in genetics, aggregate the effects of individual genetic variants to predict complex traits and disease risk ([Choi et al., 2020](#); [Lewis & Vassos, 2020](#); [Khera et al., 2018](#)). More recently, it has been inspired and translated from genetics to neuroimaging research, introducing the Polyconnectomic Scoring (PCS) ([Libedinsky et al., 2023](#); [Libedinsky et al., 2024](#)) and Polyneuro Risk Score (PNRS) ([Byington et al., 2023](#); [Mooney et al., 2024](#)), which utilize a weighted aggregation of all brain features based on their associations. Additionally, Connectome-based Predictive Modeling (CPM) exemplifies the most widely used MUA method in neuroimaging that uses a binary feature selection step based on association, followed by aggregation of selected brain features ([Shen et al., 2017](#); [Finn et al., 2015](#)). The simplicity of these approaches is a key strength of MUA. Since the core of these algorithms relies on a simple mass univariate regression step, these methods remain highly interpretable. Furthermore, in practice, they often achieve prediction performance comparable to that of more complex algorithms.

Despite sharing fundamental computational principles, these methods feature widely different implementation details in practice and are not yet connected with a standard machine learning workflow. CPM is primarily implemented in MATLAB with code from Yale (<https://github.com/YaleMRRC/CPM>), while PNRS is implemented in MATLAB with code from the Developmental Cognition and Neuroimaging (DCAN) lab at the University of Minnesota (<https://github.com/DCAN-Labs/BWAS/tree/main>). Moreover, the main implementation for calculating the PRS in genetics is implemented in an R package, which incorporates various domain-specific analytical processes unique to the field of genetics (<https://choishingwan.github.io/PRS-Tutorial/>).

It is important to note that we don't focus on PCS in this paper, as we are unable to find an implementation of PCS that extracts the weights (referred to in that work as the “connectome summary statistics (CSS) matrix”) from the input data at present. They utilize a CSS matrix, which they previously extracted from many high sample datasets for different disorders ([Libedinsky et al., 2024](#)).

Here, we present a unified, open-source, and configurable pipeline that consolidates established mass univariate methods into a single platform compatible with modern machine learning workflows in Python and validate it by reproducing results from published pipelines using the Human Connectome Project (HCP) dataset ([Van Essen et al., 2013](#)). Built within the scikit-learn architecture, this fully parametrized pipeline enables researchers to apply MUA approaches, including CPM and PNRS, while leveraging the comprehensive scikit-learn ecosystem. Users can access the full range of cross-validation strategies, evaluation metrics, hyperparameter optimization tools, various regression methods, and pipeline variations that enable developers to extend and customize the framework according to their specific research needs.

By providing a unified platform for mass univariate connectivity methods, we aim to accelerate methodological development, reduce programming errors for researchers, and enhance reproducibility in brain-behavior prediction research.

2. A Configurable Pipeline for Mass Univariate Aggregation Methods

2.1 Unified Configurable Pipeline Overview

We developed a unified, configurable computational pipeline that integrates established methods, such as CPM ([Shen et al., 2017](#)) and PRNS ([Byington et al., 2023](#)), alongside novel analytical approaches through a single interface. The pipeline's core is built around two classes—FeatureVectorizer and MUA—both of which are engineered to be fully compatible with the scikit-learn ecosystem. By inheriting from BaseEstimator and TransformerMixin, these classes implement the standard estimator interface (fit, predict, and score), ensuring seamless interoperability with Python's broader machine learning infrastructure.

This modular architecture allows researchers to leverage sophisticated scikit-learn features for standardized analysis, including automated hyperparameter optimization via GridSearchCV and RandomizedSearchCV. Furthermore, the pipeline is designed to be model-agnostic, that can handle any scikit-learn regression method to suit specific research needs; by adjusting parameters within this framework, researchers can exactly reproduce existing methods, create hybrid approaches, or develop entirely new strategies while maintaining consistent cross-validation protocols (e.g., 10-fold cross-validation) and diverse evaluation metrics (e.g., mean squared error).

2.1.1 FeatureVectorizer Class

The FeatureVectorizer class helps to handle both 2D and 3D input data. In this manner, our configurable pipeline can be used to apply MUA methods on neuroimaging data (connectivity matrices) and any other feature-outcome data.

2.1.2 MUA Class

The MUA class is our main Python class that extends scikit-learn's BaseEstimator and TransformerMixin classes to ensure compatibility with standard machine learning pipelines; the MUA class operates through three steps:

- 1. Feature Selection and Organization:** Determines which features are included and how they are organized (e.g., split into positive/negative networks or combined)
- 2. Feature Weighting:** Specifies how selected features are weighted (e.g., binary, correlation-based, or regression-derived weights)
- 3. Feature Aggregation:** Defines how weighted features are combined into predictive scores (e.g., sum or mean aggregation)

The output of the MUA class is both the aggregated and weighted features.

2.1.3 Prediction Strategy

Some approaches, such as CPM ([Shen et al., 2017](#)), include an additional step, which is applying a regression method (e.g., linear regression) on the final weighted features for prediction. In this case, after indicating the MUA class parameters, users can use scikit-learn's regression methods directly in order to apply regression on the weighted features. For more information and clarification, please refer to **Table 1** and section **2.4.1.1**.

Figure 1. Overview of the unified configurable pipeline inputs and outputs for applying mass univariate aggregation methods. (a) Input data for the pipeline includes a matrix of features (n subjects \times m predictors); (e.g., connectivity edges), and a vector of observations (n subjects; e.g., behavioral measures) as the input. (b) The key parameters that are used for setting up the algorithm are mentioned here (for full descriptions of each parameter's options, see Table 1). (c) At the end, we can compare the predicted values for each subject to actual values for each subject via correlation, absolute and mean squared errors, and the full host of other performance metrics available in scikit-learn. Illustration in (a) shows data for 4 toy subjects, and (b) shows predicted and actual values for a toy set of 65 subjects.

2.2 Implementation Details

2.2.1 FeatureVectorizer Class

The FeatureVectorizer is designed to standardize symmetric graph input data for passing through the MUA class. When handling 3D connectivity input—represented as n subjects \times m regions \times m regions—it efficiently vectorizes the data by extracting only the off-diagonal upper triangular elements. If the input is already in a 2D feature format, the vectorizer leaves the data unmodified. Furthermore, the class supports inverse transformation, enabling the reconstruction of full symmetric matrices from feature vectors for subsequent usage.

2.2.2 MUA Class

The MUA class employs seven configurable parameters (Table 1) organized across the four computational steps described above that enable flexible implementation of established methods while facilitating exploration of novel approaches.

Parameter	Value	Description
split_by_sign	True	Separate positive/negative features
	False	Keep all features together
selection_method	'all'	Use all features
	'pvalue'	Select features with $p < \alpha$
	'top_k'	Select the top k features by absolute correlation
selection_threshold	float (0, 1)	'pvalue' method: p-value threshold
	integer	'top_k' method: number of features
	N/A	For 'all' method: ignore it
weighting_method	'binary'	± 1 based on correlation sign
	'correlation'	The strength of the correlation
	'squared_correlation'	r^2 preserving sign

	'regression'	feature-specific regression coefficients
Correlation Type	'pearson'	Linear correlation
	'spearman'	Rank-based correlation
feature_aggregation	'sum'	The sum of the weighted features
	'mean'	The mean of the weighted features
standardize_scores	True	Z-score normalize final scores
	False	Keep raw scores

Table 1. Core parameters of the MUA class, which is the main part of the unified configurable pipeline for feature-based predictive modeling. Each parameter controls a specific aspect of the algorithmic workflow, enabling flexible configuration of mass univariate aggregation methods.

2.2.3 Prediction Strategy

As detailed in Section 2.1.3, our configurable pipeline facilitates the use of the various regression options available in scikit-learn. The following section demonstrates the practical application of this approach:

```
The_pipeline = Pipeline([
    ('vectorize', FeatureVectorizer()),
    ('mua', MUA(
        ...,
        ...
    )),
```

```

('regressor', LinearRegression()) # Linear regression
])

```

While `LinearRegression()` is used here as an example, the pipeline supports the integration of any alternative Scikit-learn regression method.

2.4 Common Neuroimaging Algorithms and Their Pipeline Configurations

2.4.1 Connectome-based Predictive Modeling Algorithm (CPM)

CPM ([Shen et al., 2017](#)) identifies connectivity patterns that predict individual differences in behavior through sign-based aggregation.

Figure 2. Connectome-based Predictive Modeling (CPM) algorithm workflow. (a) For each subject, functional connectivity matrices are extracted, where each element represents the correlation between brain regions. Features (connectivity edges) are selected based on their correlation with the behavioral measure, using a significance threshold ($p < \alpha$). (b) Selected edges are partitioned into positive (red) and negative (blue) networks based on correlation sign. For each subject, positive and negative network strength scores (PS and NS) are calculated as the sum of connectivity values within each network. (c) A linear regression model combines the network scores to predict behavior ($\hat{y} = \beta_0 + \beta_1(NS) + \beta_2(PS) + \epsilon$). Model performance is evaluated by correlating predicted and actual behavioral values. (d) The scatter plot shows prediction accuracy, with the red dashed line indicating perfect prediction. The distribution of prediction errors illustrates model performance across subjects.

This method employs a straightforward four-step approach:

Step 1: Feature Selection Let X be the connectivity matrix with n subjects and m features, where x_{ij} represents the connectivity value for subject j and feature i . Let y be the behavioral measure vector for all subjects.

For each connectivity feature i (where $i = 1, \dots, m$), compute the Pearson correlation coefficient r_i between feature vector x_i and behavioral measure y , along with its corresponding p-value p_i .

Given a significance threshold α (typically 0.05), select features based on statistical significance:
 $S = \{i: p_i < \alpha\}$

where S is the set of indices for selected features.

Step 2: Sign-Based Aggregation Partition the selected features S into two subsets based on their correlation sign:

$$\text{Positive feature set: } S_+ = \{i \in S : r_i > 0\}$$

$$\text{Negative feature set: } S_- = \{i \in S : r_i < 0\}$$

For each subject j , compute two aggregate scores:

$$\text{Positive network score: } PS_j = \sum_{i \in S_+} x_{ij}$$

$$\text{Negative network score: } NS_j = \sum_{i \in S_-} x_{ij}$$

This binary weighting approach assigns equal importance to all selected features regardless of correlation magnitude.

Step 3: Behavioral Prediction Fit a linear regression model using the positive and negative network scores as predictors. For each subject, the predicted behavioral value \hat{y}_j is:

$$\hat{y}_j = \beta_0 + \beta_1 PS_j + \beta_2 NS_j$$

where β_0 is the intercept, β_1 and β_2 are regression coefficients estimated via least squares.

Step 4: Evaluation Assess the prediction accuracy by computing the Pearson correlation coefficient r and its associated p-value p :

$$r, p = \text{cor}(y, \hat{y})$$

where y is the vector of actual behavioral values and \hat{y} is the vector of predicted values.

2.4.1.1 CPM Configuration

The traditional CPM ([Shen et al., 2017](#)) algorithm can be implemented within our configurable pipeline using the following configuration:

```

cpm_pipeline = Pipeline([
    ('vectorize', FeatureVectorizer()),
    ('mua', MUA(
        split_by_sign=True,
        selection_method='pvalue',
        selection_threshold=0.05,
        weighting_method='binary',
        feature_aggregation='sum',
    )),
    ('regressor', LinearRegression()) # Linear regression
])

# Cross-validation
cpm_scores = cross_val_score(cpm_pipeline,
Functional_connectivity_matrices, behavioral_measures, cv=10)
cpm_predictions = cross_val_predict(cpm_pipeline,
Functional_connectivity_matrices, behavioral_measures, cv=10)
print(f"CPM R2 (10-fold CV): {cpm_scores.mean():.3f} ±
{cpm_scores.std():.3f}")

# Evaluation
cpm_r, cpm_p = pearsonr(behavioral_measures,
cpm_predictions)

mae = mean_absolute_error(behavioral_measures,
cpm_predictions)

rmse = np.sqrt(mean_squared_error(behavioral_measures,
cpm_predictions))

r2 = r2_score(behavioral_measures, cpm_predictions)
cpm_scores = cross_val_score(cpm_pipeline,
Functional_connectivity_matrices, behavioral_measures, cv=10)
cpm_predictions = cross_val_predict(cpm_pipeline,
Functional_connectivity_matrices, behavioral_measures, cv=10)

```

The key parameters in the MUA class that define CPM are:

- `split_by_sign=True` creates separate positive and negative network scores
- `selection_method='pvalue'` with `threshold=0.05` implements statistical feature selection
- `weighting_method='binary'` assigns equal weights to all selected features (connectivity edge)
- `feature_aggregation='sum'` computes network strength as the sum of selected features

2.4.2 Polynuro Risk Score Algorithm (PNRS)

PNRS (Byington et al., 2023) predicts individual differences in behavior through association-weighted aggregation, where each connectivity edge contributes proportionally to its univariate predictive strength.

Figure 3. Polynuro Risk Score (PNRS) methodology. (a) Functional connectivity matrices are represented for multiple subjects, with brain regions color-coded according to network assignment. Each subject's connectivity data contains features from all brain region pairs. (b) For each connectivity feature across all subjects, univariate regression coefficients (β weights) are calculated using the model $y = \beta \times \text{feature}$, where y represents the behavioral measure. This produces one β weight per feature, with examples shown for features f_1 through f_{10} . (c) PNRS calculation for each subject j : The score is computed as the sum of all connectivity features multiplied by their corresponding β weights ($\hat{y}_j = \beta_1 f_{1,j} + \beta_2 f_{2,j} + \dots + \beta_{10} f_{10,j}$). (d) Model evaluation showing the correlation between PNRS-predicted values and actual behavioral measures (left), with prediction errors displayed as a histogram (right). The red dashed line indicates perfect prediction.

The method proceeds through four steps:

Step 1: Feature Selection Let X be the connectivity matrix with n subjects and m features, where x_{ij} represents the connectivity value for subject j and feature i . Let y be the behavioral measure vector for all subjects.

All m connectivity features are retained without selection. For each feature i (where $i = 1, \dots, m$), compute the univariate regression coefficient β_i from the model:

$$y = \beta_i x_i$$

where x_i is the vector of connectivity values for feature i across all subjects, and the coefficient is computed as:

$$\beta_i = (x_i^T y) / (x_i^T x_i)$$

Step 2: Weighted Feature Aggregation For each subject j , compute a single aggregated score S_j by summing all features weighted by their regression coefficients:

$$S_j = \sum_{i=1}^m \beta_i x_{ij}$$

This creates a composite score that reflects the cumulative effect of all brain features.

Step 3: Direct Prediction The aggregated scores S serve directly as the predicted behavioral values \hat{y} :

$$\hat{y}_j = S_j \text{ for each subject } j$$

Step 4: Evaluation Assess the prediction accuracy by computing the Pearson correlation coefficient r and its associated p-value p :

$$r, p = \text{cor}(y, \hat{y})$$

where y is the vector of actual behavioral values and \hat{y} is the vector of predicted values.

2.4.2.1 PNRS Configuration

The PNRS ([Byington et al., 2023](#)) algorithm can be implemented within our configurable pipeline using the following configuration. This configuration uses all connectivity features without selection, creating a comprehensive brain-wide score.

```
pnrs_pipeline = Pipeline([
    ('vectorize', FeatureVectorizer()),
    ('mua', MUA(
```

```

        split_by_sign=False,
        selection_method='all',
        weighting_method='regression',
        feature_aggregation='sum',
    ))
])

pnrs_scores =
pnrs_pipeline.fit_transform(Functional_connectivity_matrices,
behavioral_measures)

# Use scores directly as predictions
pnrs_predictions = pnrs_scores.flatten()

# Evaluation
pnrs_r, pnrs_p = pearsonr(behavioral_measures,
pnrs_predictions)

mae = mean_absolute_error(behavioral_measures,
pnrs_predictions)

rmse = np.sqrt(mean_squared_error(behavioral_measures,
pnrs_predictions))

r2 = r2_score(behavioral_measures, pnrs_predictions)

```

The key parameters in the MUA class that define PNRS are:

- `split_by_sign=False` maintains a single combined score across all features (connectivity edges)
- `selection_method='all'` includes every feature without statistical thresholding
- `weighting_method='regression'` assigns beta weights from univariate regressions ($\beta = X'y / X'X$)
- `feature_aggregation='sum'` computes the polyneuro score as a weighted sum of all features

3. Validation: Reproducing Published Results

To ensure the accuracy of our unified pipeline, we compared the results of our pipeline configurations for CPM ([Shen et al., 2017](#)), `split_by_sign=True`, `selection_method='pvalue'` with `threshold=0.05`, `weighting_method='binary'`, `feature_aggregation='sum'`, and PNRS ([Byington et al., 2023](#)), `split_by_sign=False`, `selection_method='all'`, `weighting_method='regression'`, `feature_aggregation='sum'`, with the associated established MATLAB implementations (CPM: <https://github.com/YaleMRRC/CPM/tree/master>; PNRS: <https://github.com/DCAN-Labs/BWAS/tree/main>). The MUA methods achieved numerical equivalence compared with established implementations. Complete validation scripts are available in our repository's "Validation" directory.

3.1 Dataset

We validated these pipelines using resting-state fMRI data obtained from the HCP ([Van Essen et al., 2013](#)). The dataset comprised 1067 subjects. Functional connectivity matrices were derived by preprocessing the data using the Yale preprocessing and functional connectivity estimation pipelines (cf. [Noble et al.](#)) to obtain resting-state functional connectivity data as the Pearson correlations between time series for each region of the Shen268 atlas, yielding 268×268 symmetric matrices per subject. Following the original CPM ([Shen et al., 2017](#)), fluid intelligence scores served as the behavioral prediction target.

3.2 CPM Validation We benchmarked our CPM implementation against the original Yale code ([Shen et al., 2017](#); <https://github.com/YaleMRRC/CPM/tree/master>). Using identical 10-fold cross-validation with the threshold of 0.05 for finding significant associations, our pipeline created positive and negative network strength scores and had the same final behavioral predictions ($r \sim 0.22$, $p < 0.001$). The performance metrics between implementations validate the ability to faithfully reproduce the standard CPM algorithm, including its characteristic separation of positive and negative networks combined through linear regression.

Figure 4 presents the results from the original MATLAB CPM implementation alongside the results from our pipeline.

Figure 4. Performance comparison between the original MATLAB implementation and the reproduced CPM within the Python pipeline. The top panel (Original) and bottom panel (Configurable Pipeline) display: (A) Correlations between actual and predicted behavioral scores (Original: $r = 0.225$; Pipeline: $r = 0.221$; both $p < 0.001$). (B) The pipeline achieves results consistent with the original implementation, with closely matched metrics (Original: MAE = 3.928, RMSE = 4.745; Pipeline: MAE = 3.952, RMSE = 4.748). Both sets of results were obtained via 10-fold cross-validation on HCP connectivity data. The Python pipeline was configured to replicate the original logic using: `split_by_sign=True`, `selection_method='pvalue'`, `selection_threshold=0.05`, `weighting_method='binary'`, `feature_aggregation='sum'`, and `use_final_regression=True`.

3.3 PNRS Validation

We validated our PNRS implementation against the DCAN Labs BWAS toolbox ([Byington et al., 2023](https://github.com/DCAN-Labs/BWAS/tree/main); <https://github.com/DCAN-Labs/BWAS/tree/main>). We validated our PNRS implementation against the DCAN Labs BWAS toolbox ([Byington et al., 2023](https://github.com/DCAN-Labs/BWAS/tree/main); <https://github.com/DCAN-Labs/BWAS/tree/main>). As shown in Figure 5, the performance of the reproduced PNRS within our configurable Python pipeline is numerically identical to the original MATLAB implementation. Both versions achieved a correlation of $r = 0.152$ ($p < 0.001$) and yielded matching error metrics. The exact correspondence of correlation coefficients and error metrics between implementations validates the ability of our pipeline to reproduce the PNRS methodology through appropriate parameter configuration faithfully.

Figure 5. Comparative performance of the original MATLAB implementation and the reproduced PNRS within the Python pipeline. The top row (Original) and bottom row (Configurable Pipeline) illustrate: (A) Correlations between actual and predicted behavioral scores, showing identical results ($r = 0.152$, $p < 0.001$). (B) Distributions of prediction errors with normal distribution fits; both implementations produced exact numerical matches for performance metrics (MAE = 164,515.113; RMSE = 166,478.006). The Python pipeline was configured with the following parameters to ensure parity: `split_by_sign=False`, `selection_method='all'`, `weighting_method='regression'`, `feature_aggregation='sum'`, and `use_final_regression=False`.

4. Discussion

The primary contribution of this work is the technical consolidation of MUA methods into a single, standardized, and configurable pipeline. Built within the scikit-learn ecosystem in Python, this unified framework pipeline established two frequently used techniques—CPM (Shen et al., 2017) and PNRS (Byington et al., 2023), which we have validated against their original code—alongside hybrid approaches and novel analytical strategies. By providing comprehensive documentation and validation scripts, we minimize implementation errors and significantly enhance reproducibility in brain-behavior prediction studies.

Furthermore, our pipeline addresses a critical accessibility gap: while the original implementations of CPM ([Shen et al., 2017](#)) and PNRS ([Byington et al., 2023](#)) were originally developed in MATLAB, which is not an open-source tool, our Python implementation offers a more accessible and free alternative for the broader research community. This approach enables researchers to apply these two validated techniques within a modern analytical framework while maintaining exact numerical reproducibility with the original source code.

4.1 Recommendations & Future Work

For optimal results using our configurable pipeline, we recommend following standard machine learning best practices: (1) ensuring adequate sample sizes based on recent neuroimaging guidelines ([Marek et al., 2022](#); [Scheinost et al., 2019](#)); (2) performing the “Preprocessing” script available in our repository which helps to remove faulty subjects; (3) carefully selecting method parameters aligned with research objectives; and (4) comprehensively reporting all methodological details ([Poldrack et al., 2017](#); [Varoquaux & Colliot, 2023](#)).

While our current implementation faithfully reproduces established MUA methods, including CPM and PNRS, the parameterized configurable pipeline opens exciting possibilities for methodological innovation. Future work will systematically characterize performance across the full parameter space, exploring hybrid configurations such as: (1) combinations of weighting methods (e.g., correlation-based weights for feature selection with regression weights for aggregation); (2) ensemble approaches that combine predictions from multiple parameter configurations. The pipeline infrastructure is also flexible for developers to contribute other mass univariate methods that may be of interest.

4.2 Conclusion

Our pipeline significantly simplifies the reporting process; users can achieve full methodological transparency by directly documenting the specific input parameters passed to the function. By utilizing these built-in parameters to define the MUA class, standardization, and cross-validation strategy, researchers can seamlessly provide the documentation necessary for exact reproducibility and cross-study comparisons ([Scheinost et al., 2019](#)). By providing this unified platform with comprehensive parameter control, which facilitates application of validated MUA methods and systematic exploration of the MUA design space using standardized machine learning toolkits, this pipeline is intended to provide a more usable, standardized foundation for advancing our understanding of brain-behavior relationships.

5. Data availability

All raw data used in the present study have been made publicly available by HCP in accordance with data use and access regulations set by the HCP ([Van Essen et al., 2013](#)). The Northeastern University and Yale University Human Research Protection Programs approved secondary

analyses of these datasets. Human Connectome Project (HCP) data are available through the HCP repository (<https://www.humanconnectome.org/study/hcp-young-adult>). Users must agree to data use terms before accessing ConnectomeDB; details are provided at <https://www.humanconnectome.org/study/hcp-young-adult/data-use-terms>.

6. Code availability

All code used for running statistical analyses has been made publicly available on GitHub at https://github.com/FatemehDoshvargar/_MUA_Pipeline. The BioImage Suite command line software used for processing is freely available at (<https://bioimagesuiteweb.github.io/webapp/index.html>).

7. Acknowledgements

This work was supported by funding from the National Institute of Mental Health (R00 MH130894 to S.N). Data were provided by the Human Connectome Project, WU-Minn Consortium (Principal Investigators: David Van Essen and Kamil Ugurbil; 1U54MH091657) funded by the 16 NIH Institutes and Centers that support the NIH Blueprint for Neuroscience Research; and by the McDonnell Center for Systems Neuroscience at Washington University.

8. Contribution statement

S.N. conceived of the study. F.D. performed all analyses and interpretation under the guidance of S.N.. F.C. provided additional guidance on code implementation, and H.S. provided additional guidance on interpretation. F.D. wrote the manuscript with input from all co-authors.

References

1. Rosenberg MD, Finn ES, Scheinost D, Papademetris X, Shen X, Constable RT, Chun MM. A neuromarker of sustained attention from whole-brain functional connectivity. *Nature Neuroscience*. 2016;19(1):165-171. <https://doi.org/10.1038/nn.4179>
2. Finn ES, Shen X, Scheinost D, Rosenberg MD, Huang J, Chun MM, Papademetris X, Constable RT. Functional connectome fingerprinting: identifying individuals using patterns of brain connectivity. *Nature Neuroscience*. 2015;18(11):1664-1671. <https://doi.org/10.1038/nn.4135>
3. Dubois J, Adolphs R. Building a science of individual differences from fMRI. *Trends in Cognitive Sciences*. 2016;20(6):425-443. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tics.2016.03.014>
4. Scheinost D, Noble S, Horien C, Greene AS, Lake EMR, Salehi M, Gao S, Shen X, O'Connor D, Barron DS, et al. Ten simple rules for predictive modeling of individual differences in neuroimaging. *NeuroImage*. 2019;193:35-45. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.neuroimage.2019.02.057>

5. Shen X, Finn ES, Scheinost D, Rosenberg MD, Chun MM, Papademetris X, Constable RT. Using connectome-based predictive modeling to predict individual behavior from brain connectivity. *Nature Protocols*. 2017;12(3):506-518. <https://doi.org/10.1038/nprot.2016.178>
6. Whitfield-Gabrieli S, Wendelken C, Nieto-Castañón A, Bailey SK, Anteraper SA, Lee YJ, Chai XQ, Hirshfeld-Becker DR, Biederman J, Cutting LE, Bunge SA. Association of intrinsic brain architecture with changes in attentional and mood symptoms during development. *JAMA Psychiatry*. 2020;77(4):378-386. <https://doi.org/10.1001/jamapsychiatry.2019.4208>
7. Lewis CM, Vassos E. Polygenic risk scores: from research tools to clinical instruments. *Genome Medicine*. 2020;12(1):44. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s13073-020-00742-5>
8. Choi SW, Mak TSH, O'Reilly PF. Tutorial: a guide to performing polygenic risk score analyses. *Nature Protocols*. 2020;15(9):2759-2772. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41596-020-0353-1>
9. Khera AV, Chaffin M, Aragam KG, Haas ME, Roselli C, Choi SH, Natarajan P, Lander ES, Lubitz SA, Ellinor PT, Kathiresan S. Genome-wide polygenic scores for common diseases identify individuals with risk equivalent to monogenic mutations. *Nature Genetics*. 2018;50(9):1219-1224. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41588-018-0183-z>
10. Libedinsky I, Helweggen K, Dannlowski U, Fornito A, Repple J, Zalesky A, Breakspear M, Boonstra TW. Polyconnectomic scoring of functional connectivity patterns across eight neuropsychiatric and three neurodegenerative disorders. *Biological Psychiatry*. 2024;95(7):647-657. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biopsych.2023.07.012>
11. Libedinsky I, Helweggen K, Boonstra TW, Repple J, Kircher T, Dannlowski U, Fornito A, Breakspear M, Zalesky A. Polyconnectome scores of brain functional connectivity predict behavior, cognition, and psychopathology across the lifespan. 2023. bioRxiv 2023.10.25.564060. <https://doi.org/10.1101/2023.10.25.564060>
12. Byington EA, Prem S, Chandrasekaran S, Hendrickson TJ, Duda TA, Sathyaputri L, Maki PM, Hippman C, Greven CU, Faraone SV, Tiemeier H. PolyNeuro Risk Scores capture widely distributed connectivity patterns of cognition. *Developmental Cognitive Neuroscience*. 2023;60:101231. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.dcn.2023.101231>
13. Mooney MA, Bhatt P, Hermosillo RJ, Ryabinin P, Nikolas MA, Faraone SV, Fair DA, Wilmot B, Nigg JT. Smaller total brain volume but not subcortical structure volume related to common genetic risk for ADHD. *Psychological Medicine*. 2021;51(8):1279-1288. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0033291719004148>
14. Van Essen DC, Smith SM, Barch DM, Behrens TEJ, Yacoub E, Ugurbil K, for the WU-Minn HCP Consortium. The WU-Minn Human Connectome Project: an overview. *NeuroImage*. 2013;80:62-79. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.neuroimage.2013.05.041>
15. Adelstein JS, Shehzad Z, Mennes M, DeYoung CG, Zuo XN, Kelly C, Margulies DS, Bloomfield A, Gray JR, Castellanos FX, Milham MP. Personality is reflected in the

- brain's intrinsic functional architecture. *PLoS One*. 2011;6(11):e27633.
<https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0027633>
16. YaleMRRRC. Connectome-based Predictive Modeling (CPM). GitHub repository.
<https://github.com/YaleMRRRC/CPM>
 17. DCAN-Labs. Brain-Wide Association Study (BWAS) Toolbox. GitHub repository.
<https://github.com/DCAN-Labs/BWAS>
 18. Marek, S., et al. (2022). Reproducible brain-wide association studies require thousands of individuals. *Nature*, 603(7902), 654-660. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41586-022-04492-9>
 19. Poldrack, R. A., et al. (2017). Scanning the horizon: towards transparent and reproducible neuroimaging research. *Nature Reviews Neuroscience*, 18(2), 115-126.
<https://doi.org/10.1038/nrn.2016.167>
 20. Scheinost, D., et al. (2019). Ten simple rules for predictive modeling of individual differences in neuroimaging. *NeuroImage*, 193, 35-45.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.neuroimage.2019.02.057>
 21. Varoquaux, G., & Colliot, O. (2023). Evaluating machine learning models and their diagnostic value. *Machine Learning for Brain Disorders*, 601-630. <https://hal.science/hal-03681442>